

exhibits three absorption bands at 8.8(6), 14.7(10) and 25.0(15) k.k. assignable⁷ to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2T_{1g}$ (P)⁸ transitions respectively characteristic of high-spin octahedral or distorted octahedral configuration. Copper(II) complex shows one broad absorption band at 15.5 (45) k.k. indicating probably a tetragonally distorted octahedral configuration. On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral data zinc(II) complexes presumably have an octahedral environment around the metal ion.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Some Rare Earths With EDTA as Primary Ligand and 2,3-Dihydroxynaphthalene-6-Sulphonic Acid as Secondary Ligand : A Potentiometric Study

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In recent years, the study of the mixed ligand complexes of the rare earths has become of great interest, as its existence gives an evidence for the rare earths to have a coordination number greater than six and also offers an alternative reaction to the hydrolysis andolation of rare earths in binary complexes.

In the present paper, evidence for the mixed ligand complex formation are summarised which thereby explains the expansion in coordination number of rare earths due to replacement of water molecules by the second ligand. The stability constants of the binary and ternary complexes have been determined by using an extension of the Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique¹ to the mixed ligand complexes.

Experimental

The chemicals used during these investigations were of *analar* grade. The stock solution of 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene-6-sulphonic acid (Light and Co. Ltd.), 0.01 M was prepared in double distilled water. Other solutions were prepared as described in previous papers.²⁻⁴ Experimental set up, instruments used, systems prepared etc. were same as in earlier studies²⁻⁴

Results and Discussion

The 'Practical' proton-ligand stability constants were obtained by the methods of interpolation at various \bar{n}_A -values (Method A) and interpolation at half \bar{n}_A -values (Method B). The values of $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ were found to be 11.39 and 8.10 (Method A), and 11.42 and 8.11 (Method B), respectively.

The stability constants of the binary complexes were obtained as reported earlier.^{2,8} The value of \bar{n} in the metal-ligand formation curve exceeded 1.5 which reveals the formation of 1 : 1 as well as 1 : 2 complexes. The values of 1 : 1 complexes only have been used for comparison purposes and are reported in Table 1.

The stability constants for the ternary complexes were evaluated as in previous paper⁴ The value of \bar{n} does not exceed 0.9 or 1.0 which shows the formation of only 1 : 1 : 1 mixed-ligand complex. The values obtained are tabulated in Table 1.

TABLE-1 STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES OF DHNSA

$t = 30^\circ\text{C}$ and $\mu = 0.2 \text{ M NaClO}_4$

Metal	Binary		Ternary	
	A	B	A	B
Sc(III)	14.15	14.11	7.27	7.22
Y(III)	10.09	10.06	6.83	6.81
La(III)	8.35	8.31	4.68	4.64
Pr(III)	8.96	8.94	5.43	5.40
Nd(III)	9.10	9.03	5.60	5.57
Sm(III)	9.68	9.73	6.30	6.32

For all the rare earths, the stability constants of mixed ligand complexes are less than those of the corresponding (1 : 1) binary complexes which can be explained on the basis of electrostatic forces and space available for the second incoming ligand. In the present study, EDTA being a hexadentate ligand, occupies all the six coordination sites and thus satisfies the characteristic coordination number of six. Now to accommodate second ligand which is bidentate in nature, water molecules at seventh and eighth coordination sites are to be displaced. The formation of only 1 : 1 : 1 mixed-ligand chelate reveals the coordination number of eight for the

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rare earths in the present case. The trend of stability constants of binary as well as ternary complexes follows the order $\text{Sc(III)} > \text{Y(III)} > \text{Sm(III)} > \text{Nd(III)} > \text{Pr(III)} > \text{La(III)}$ i. e., stability decreases with the increase in ionic radii.

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Kinetics of Oxidation of Succinic Acid by Cerium(IV) Sulphate in Acidic Medium

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THE Survey of the literature shows that a systematic kinetic study of the oxidation of aliphatic acids like oxalic^{1,2}, malonic³⁻⁵, succinic and glutaric acids has not received any attention so far. The present study deals the oxidation of succinic acid by cerium(IV) in presence of sulphuric acid.

Experimental

The chemicals used were either "AnalaR or E. Merck" guaranteed reagent quality. Cerium(IV) sulphate solution was prepared by dissolving ceric sulphate (Fluka, A. R.) in sulphuric acid. The reactive substances were brought to the thermostat temperature maintained to $\pm 0.1^\circ$ and then rapidly mixed. Aliquots were withdrawn at known intervals of time and reaction was quenched by adding ice-cold distilled water and the unconsumed cerium(IV) was estimated with standard solution of Mohr's salt using ferroin as an indicator. The pseudo first order rate constant k was determined from the graph by plot of $\log [\text{unconsumed Ce(IV)}]$ Vs. time (t).

The order of reaction has been determined with the help of Vant Hoff's differential equation and comes out to be less than one w.r.t. Ce(IV) and succinic acid. Further the pseudo first order behaviour of the reaction w.r.t. succinic acid has been confirmed by plotting $1/k$ vs. $1/[\text{succinic acid}]$. The plot is a straight line which does not pass through the origin but it cuts $1/k$ axis at a certain distance (Fig. 1). This suggests an information of activated complex between Ce(IV) and succinic acid.

Fig 1

Effect of Sulphuric Acid

The effect of sulphuric acid on the reaction has been studied at five different concentrations of sulphuric acid as shown in Table-1.

TABLE - 1

$10^3 \times [\text{Ce(IV)}] = 0.20M$; $10^2 \times [\text{Succinic acid}] = 1.50M$;
Temp. = 60°

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25
$10^3 \times k (\text{min}^{-1})$	8.14	6.85	5.62	5.20	2.26

The plot of k vs. $1/[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]^2$ is a straight line which indicates that the rate of reaction is inversely proportional to the square of the concentration of sulphuric acid.